

Numerical slope stability analysis of deep excavations under rainfall infiltration

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Abstract

Rainfall leads to the deterioration of slope stability conditions, while intense rainfall has been commonly associated with landslides on natural or engineered slopes. Deep excavations, typically related to geo-resources exploitation, e.g., in the case of surface mining, are often affected by rainfall events that jeopardize their stability. In this work, rainfall infiltration is directly incorporated in the slope stability analysis; this investigation is currently missing from the literature as mainly empirical methods are used regarding deep excavations. The very deep slopes from lignite mines are employed as typical examples, often reaching 200m and presenting smooth inclinations and fine-grained soils. A general numerical framework was used; the safety factor's deterministic analysis was supplemented by a Monte Carlo investigation to determine the probability of failure. The importance of the involved parameters – slope geometry, rainfall intensity, and soil properties – was studied through a parametric analysis. Initially, a typical slip surface is presented, relatively deep and reaching from toe to crest. The critical mechanism was the development - after the rainfall - of a smaller and more local than the initial (before rainfall) slip surface. Although the final surface is smaller than the initial one, it can be more than 50m high denoting a significant hazard. The most influential parameters are rainfall intensity, soil permeability, and slope height. This study can serve as a basis for similar preliminary analysis in practice. Stability and reliability analysis reveals the need to supplement conventional safety factors with the probability of failure for a broader and improved overview.

Keywords: coal mines, lignite mines, unsaturated soil mechanics, limit equilibrium method, probability of failure, Monte Carlo simulations

1. Introduction

Rainfall, in general, leads to the deterioration of slope stability conditions, while intense rainfall, in particular, has been commonly associated with landslides on natural or engineered slopes (e.g., Abramson et al. 2001; Chowdhury et al. 2009). The influence of rainfall has long been identified as a critical parameter on slope stability problems of all types (Chowdhury and Nguyen 1987; Kavvas et al. 1992; Pariseau et al. 1997; Robinson et al. 2016; Rouainia et al. 2020; Steiakakis et al. 2009).

Due to climate change, the occurrence of extreme rainfalls, either in the form of short-duration and high-intensity events or of prolonged and low-intensity events, is anticipated to be more frequent in the near future (Myhre et al. 2019). Thus, rainfall is identified as a critical factor contributing to the deterioration of slope stability worldwide. Henceforth, engineers dealing with infrastructure, mining, and other geo-activities must be appropriately prepared for addressing the unprecedented climate-driven future challenges affecting geotechnical stability (Ho et al. 2017).

In civil infrastructure projects, methods of slope stability analysis have progressed tremendously, employing advanced soil mechanics and hydrological concepts to incorporate rainfall infiltration into numerical modeling and design (Alonso et al. 2003; Cai and Ugai 2004; Lin and Zhong 2019; Rahardjo et al. 2007). Nonetheless, these slopes' height is rarely larger than 30m.

On the other hand, the effect of precipitation on slope stability of deep mining excavations (often up to 200m deep) has been investigated based mainly on observations and empirical correlations between precipitation and slopes' displacements (e.g., Kavvas et al. 2020; Steiakakis et al. 2016). In this type of analysis, rain is considered indirectly without any insight into mobilized mechanisms and stress-strain responses. Nonetheless, during rainfall infiltration, stability analysis of such slopes requires special attention for adequately

considering the effect of height on stability conditions. Few works exist that investigate rainfall's infiltration effect in the safety of deep and very deep excavations; these works are mostly back analyses of case studies rather than systematic investigations (Bo et al. 2019; Zhao and You 2020).

The present work systematically examines the slope stability of deep excavations under rainfall infiltration through an extensive numerical investigation. The study focuses on lignite (brown coal) mining, where very deep excavations (up to 200m) on fine-grained soils are employed as typical examples. Commonly, these excavations are characterized by smooth inclinations and soils with low permeability, so instability during rainfall is mainly related to the dissipation of matric suctions in unsaturated soil zones (Fredlund and Barbour 1992; Rahardjo et al. 2019).

A general numerical framework was used to analyze the stability of the slopes under the effect of rainfall infiltration. This framework combined (a) the finite element method for computation of pore water pressures changes due to rainfall, (b) the limit equilibrium method for stability assessment in terms of the safety factor, and (c) the Monte Carlo simulation method for the reliability assessment of stability. Analyses were conducted considering the soil's friction angle and cohesion (i.e., the shear strength parameters) as random variables. The geotechnical uncertainty was explicitly considered, and the probability of slope failure was computed.

In addition, given the rainfall infiltration and the consideration of shear strength parameters as random variables, the relative contribution of six other critical parameters was investigated through parametric studies. In particular, the parameters evaluated were the influence of the height and inclination of the slope, the rainfall intensity, the initial groundwater level, the soil permeability, and the soil-water characteristic curve.

Overall, this study investigates the stability of deep excavations under rainfall infiltration that has been neglected in the literature. Deep excavations are common in many applications related to geo-resources; typical ones are the massive slopes of coal and lignite mines and similar surface mining activities. These deep excavations' safety is crucial during the active operation on the area and after its abandonment, e.g., regarding the valorization of closed and abandoned mines.

2. Numerical framework

An illustrative overview of the proposed framework for the probabilistic assessment of slope stability under the effect of rainfall can be seen in Figure 1. In that chart, the rectangular shape denotes a process and the oblique parallelogram information that comes into the related process from outside or leaves the process (input/output data). Three numerical methods are employed in this analysis: the Finite Element Method for the steady-state and transient seepage flow; the Limit Equilibrium Method (LEM), locating the critical slip surface and computing the corresponding safety factor (SF); the Monte Carlo Simulation (MCS) method to evaluate the probability of failure (P_F). These three methods were implemented in the slope stability analysis software Slide 8.0 (Rocscience 2021). A description of the specific analysis using these three numerical methods is provided in the following subsections.

Firstly, the slope's initial conditions are identified (Input of Geometry/Hydro-mechanical properties), and the groundwater table is calculated by considering steady-state conditions and the FEM. From this analysis, the pore water pressures are the main output used in the following stages (u_w , upper-middle oblique rectangle). The initial conditions (before rainfall) are then evaluated, following the left branch in Figure 1. Slope stability of the initial conditions is assessed using the LEM and the Safety Factor (SF) and slope reliability using the MCS and the probability of failure (P_F). These two indicators provide the main factors for assessing initial

conditions; emphasis is also given on the slip surface, and additional indicators are used as described in the following subsections.

The second branch from the pore water pressures (right branch of Figure 1) uses the initial conditions and applies a rainfall event. Rainfall characteristics are decided, and the transient analysis is solved using the FEM, providing the final pore pressures after rainfall. Based on these conditions, the slope stability and the slope reliability are evaluated similarly as before rainfall. Finally, all indicators and factors are compared before and after the rainfall to assess its effect on slope safety.

Figure 1. Numerical framework for slope stability probabilistic assessment

2.1. Seepage analysis (Finite Element Method): Steady-state flow - Transient flow

In this work, groundwater conditions were calculated for the long-term slope stability as well as the short-term time-dependent changes due to rainfall by the Finite Element Method

(FEM). The assumption of two-dimensional plane strain conditions was adopted, postulating that the outlying boundary conditions in the out-of-plane analysis space are equivalent to the analyzed representative cross-section. The representative slope's geometry was discretized by 8-noded 2,272 quadrilateral elements, forming an assemblage consisting of 7,011 nodes (Figure 2). The model's boundaries were set to minimize boundary phenomena affecting the slope stability. The boundary distances ($2H$ horizontally and H vertically) are typical and are not expected to present boundary effects, even more, due to the nature of the LEM. This has been further evaluated by increasing the boundary distances in both directions while the obtained results were practically identical.

Initially, a steady-state flow analysis simulated the long-term groundwater conditions of a deep excavation (Figure 2). The excavation's bottom was assumed as the right boundary of the steady-state groundwater flow because, typically, the excavation is emptied of water. The initial groundwater depth at the left boundary (H_w) is crucial, defining the hydraulic conditions moving away from the slope's crest. The importance of H_w will be illustrated in the sequel, particularly on the unsaturated zone's profile, which affects the stability before and after the rainfall.

Figure 2. Finite element model for steady-state and transient seepage analysis

Groundwater flow analysis is required to capture the time-dependent changes of the rainfall infiltration that lead to slope stability changes. A significant stage of this numerical analysis is assessing the unsaturated zone above the groundwater table. Within this zone, pore-pressures are negative (suction) and closely related to the degree of saturation through the soil-water characteristic curve (SWCC). The SWCC plays a crucial role in providing the information required for capturing the groundwater seepage in the unsaturated zone. It describes the capacity of the unsaturated soil to retain moisture at different stress gradients and essentially associates saturation levels with soil suction. Moreover, a relationship (called the permeability function) is required to quantify the unsaturated soil's permeability at different saturation levels, i.e., the unsaturated soil's drainage capacity.

Herein, the unsaturated soil response was captured via a particular form of the widely known van Genuchten-Mualem relationship (Mualem 1976; van Genuchten 1980). Soil's saturation S_w within the unsaturated zone is a function of suction stress, u_w :

$$S_w = S_r + (S_s - S_r) \cdot \left[1 + \left(g_a \cdot \frac{|u_w|}{\gamma_w} \right)^{g_n} \right]^{1-g_n/g_n} \quad (1)$$

where S_r denotes soil's residual saturation; S_s is the soil saturation at the saturated state; g_a and g_n are fitting parameters that govern the shape of the SWCC; γ_w is the water's unit weight.

The unsaturated permeability k_w is also a function of suction stress and is expressed by:

$$k_w = k_s \cdot \sqrt{S_e} \cdot \left[1 - \left(1 - S_e^{g_n/g_n-1} \right)^{g_n-1/g_n} \right]^2 \quad (2)$$

where S_e is the effective degree of saturation representing a normalized saturation, expressed as:

$$S_e = \frac{S_w - S_r}{S_s - S_r} \quad (3)$$

From Eqs. (2) and (3), it is remarked that the unsaturated soil permeability decreases with the decrease of soil saturation and the increase of suction stress.

A boundary flux condition was applied at the upper surface boundaries to simulate a rainfall event (Figure 2). The left, right, and bottom boundaries of the model were impermeable. The transient seepage analysis was carried out for prescribed time intervals corresponding to the duration of the selected rainfall events. This analysis quantified the time-dependent decrease of suction stresses due to the infiltrated water into the unsaturated zone. Reduced suctions deteriorate slope stability conditions and, as a result, compromise the slope's safety during rainfall. The following sub-section concisely describes the consideration of suctions in slope stability analysis.

2.2. Slope stability (Limit Equilibrium Method)

Soil shear strength (s) in the unsaturated zone increases with suction u_w since the latter yields an additional strength to the soil. The shear strength of the unsaturated soil was estimated according to Vanapalli et al. (1996):

$$s = c' + (\sigma - u_a) \cdot \tan\phi' + S_e(u_a - u_w) \tan\phi' \quad (4a)$$

where σ denotes the total stress, u_a is the pore-air pressure, u_w is the pore-water pressure, and ϕ' and c' are the effective shear strength parameters. The third term of Eq. (4a), i.e., the product of the effective saturation S_e , with the matric suction $(u_a - u_w)$, and the tangent of the effective friction angle $\tan\phi'$, quantifies the effect of suction stress on the unsaturated shear strength. Notice that within the saturated zone, pore-air pressure u_a equals pore-water pressure u_w ; hence, the soil shear strength reduces to the classic Mohr-Coulomb failure criterion, expressed in terms of effective stresses according to:

$$s = c' + \sigma' \cdot \tan\phi' \quad (4b)$$

Estimations of soil's shear strength in the unsaturated and saturated zones (Eqs. (4a) and (4b)) were integrated within a LEM framework for calculating safety factors before, during, and after rainfall. Spencer's method of slices (Spencer 1967) was employed for determining safety factors of numerous circular trial slip surfaces. The slip surface showing the minimum safety factor was identified as critical. MCS probabilistic analyses were performed at the critical slip surfaces, anticipating the effect of geotechnical uncertainty and obtaining the probability of failure. A brief description of the probabilistic framework is given in the following sub-section.

2.3. Slope reliability (Monte Carlo Simulation)

On to the conventional deterministic approach, the independent parameters of an examined problem are considered invariant. On the contrary, these parameters are deemed random variables and are explicitly characterized by an inherent variability for the probabilistic approach. Following this notion, the safety factors exhibit dispersion around a most likely value, which should converge to the deterministic one. Typically, the dispersion of the safety factor is expressed via its standard deviation $\sigma[\text{SF}]$ and the most likely value via its mean $\mu[\text{SF}]$. Probability of failure P_F , a common safety indicator, is defined as the probability of the event that the factor of safety attains values lower than unity:

$$P_F = P(\text{SF} < 1) \quad (5)$$

The stochastic Monte Carlo Simulation method was employed in this work to evaluate P_F . This method produces an iterative implementation of a performance function (in this work, the safety factor) based on a set of random parameters. Various sets of parameters were produced via a random number generator, which can yield sequences of numerous consecutive numbers following specific statistical distributions. In this way, numerous safety factors were calculated, and a statistical distribution was obtained. Within the MCS framework, the probability of failure P_F can be evaluated according to:

$$P_F = \frac{N_F}{N} \quad (6)$$

where N_F indicates the number of trials with a safety factor less than one and N denotes the total number of trials.

Apart from the probability of failure, other indicators may also be obtained from an MCS, such as the mean of the safety factor $\mu[\text{SF}]$ and the corresponding standard deviation $\sigma[\text{SF}]$, defined as:

$$\mu[\text{SF}] = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \text{SF}_i}{N} \quad (7)$$

and

$$\sigma[\text{SF}] = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \text{SF}_i^2 - \mu[\text{SF}]^2}{N - 1}} \quad (8)$$

where SF_i stands for the safety factor computed for trial i , among the total number of trials N .

Utilizing the evaluated statistical moments of SF, another helpful safety indicator is the so-called reliability index β . The reliability index indicates the number of standard deviations separating the most expected value of the safety factor and the SF value denoting failure. Since the value of SF implying failure is equal to one, the reliability index in case of a normally distributed safety factor is defined as:

$$\beta_N = \frac{\mu[\text{SF}] - 1}{\sigma[\text{SF}]} \quad (9)$$

In case of a lognormally distributed factor of safety, the reliability index is defined as:

$$\beta_{LN} = \frac{\ln \left[\frac{\mu[\text{SF}]}{\sqrt{1 + (\text{COV}[\text{SF}])^2}} \right]}{\sqrt{\ln \left[1 + (\text{COV}[\text{SF}])^2 \right]}} \quad (10)$$

where $\text{COV}[\text{SF}]$ is the coefficient of variation of the safety factor, defined as:

$$\text{COV}[\text{SF}] = \frac{\sigma[\text{SF}]}{\mu[\text{SF}]} \cdot 100 \quad (11)$$

In this work, the probability of failure is directly evaluated from the MCS procedure by Eq. (6), counting the number of slope failures and dividing them by the total number of trials. This typical way is generally more appropriate to calculate the probability of failure than through the reliability index.

3. Development and description of the parametric study

A series of analyses were performed to examine the influence of the slope height on the stability combined with rainfall analysis in various conditions. Additionally, the relative contribution of different critical factors was evaluated. A typical geometry with common soil characteristics of an open-pit lignite mining slope was employed. It is derived based on typical lignite mines in Greece (Mikroutsikos et al. 2021). However, it is also relevant to many other coal and lignite producing countries, e.g., Turkey (Tutluoglu et al. 2011), Australia (Ghadrdan et al. 2021), and the Czech Republic (Vanneschi et al. 2018).

Table 1 summarizes the geometrical and geotechnical parameters of the baseline model. The main geometrical characteristics include very deep slopes, reaching depths of 200m, and mild inclinations (Kavvas et al. 2020; Zevgolis et al. 2019). Hydro-mechanical parameters correspond to fine-grained materials related to lignite excavation areas, often classified as high plasticity silty soils, displaying medium strength and poor drainage characteristics (Mikroutsikos et al. 2021).

A moderate-intensity (Office 2007) rainfall was considered since slopes of poor drainage soils ($k_s \leq 10^{-4}$ cm/s) are not crucially affected by extreme high-intensity events (Rahimi et al. 2010). The rainfall was assumed to last for 48h (two days). The rainfall intensity range of this work is based on the soil permeability. The baseline soil permeability is $k_s = 10^{-4}$ cm/s = 3.6mm/h; thus, the mean rainfall intensity was chosen to be 3.6mm/h to represent $q/k_s=1$. Lower and

higher values were used within this range to evaluate the effect of the rainfall on higher and lower q/k_s . Notice that this range is also typical for Greek lignite mines (e.g., Theocharis et al. 2022) and similar regions.

A single value for the soil's unit weight was adopted, regardless of whether the soil lies above or below the groundwater table (Rahardjo et al. 2007). The choice of a single unit weight value for the saturated or unsaturated zone is commonly followed in commercial software and the literature. However, its effect on slope stability is not standard and varies depending on the problem. In the present case, the effect of this assumption is not significant. For instance, for the baseline case, the two scenarios were computed (one common or two different unit weights for the saturated and the unsaturated zone), and the SF difference is less than 5%. This effect is even less significant for the present work as the methodological framework, trends, and important conclusions are not affected by this change.

Table 1 also presents the range of parametric analysis. Six parameters commonly affecting the stability were chosen; each parameter was examined independently, i.e., when it varies, all the others are equal to their baseline values. The analysis intends to cover various situations in surface lignite mining areas, and therefore the range represents a variety of situations. These parameters, and their range, concern the deterministic stages of the groundwater flow (FEM) and slope stability analysis (LEM). On the other hand, the variability of selected parameters was considered for the probabilistic analysis.

Two parameters were considered random variables, the effective friction angle (ϕ') and the cohesion (c'), given that they commonly control the slope stability conditions and the resulting safety factor. The same critical slip surface, demonstrating the minimum safety factor at the deterministic analysis phase, was employed to compute the slope's probability of failure. Table 1 includes the basic statistics of these shear strength parameters, specifically their mean values, μ , standard deviations, σ , and coefficients of variations, COV. These levels of variability

were assumed to represent typical levels of variability for common conditions (Orr and Farrell 2012). Notice that even larger variability in the cohesion and friction angle is not expected to impact the results. It was assumed that the adopted random variables are normally distributed, truncated at limits corresponding to distances of three standard deviations above and below their means.

The random variables were assumed to be statistically independent, and no cross-correlation was examined. The proposed framework can directly incorporate the correlation among the random variables by implementing specific linear correlation coefficients if this is the case. However, the aim of this work was in a different direction, mainly assessing the fundamental mechanisms of rainfall infiltration's effect on deep excavations and evaluating and quantifying the effect of the various parameters. Moreover, consideration of cross-correlation, particularly between cohesion and friction angle that is the most common and crucial one, would result in a more conservative P_f . In that vein, the cross-correlation between parameters was not involved in the analysis as it would not significantly change the mechanisms and trends.

Table 1. Parameters and corresponding values

Type of parameter	Description	Baseline value	Parametric analysis	Units
Geometrical	Slope height H	150	100, 125, 175, 200	m
	Slope angle α	14	12, 13, 15, 16	°
Hydro-mechanical	Initial groundwater depth H_w	20	10, 15, 30, 40	m
	SWCC parameter g_a	0.01	0.001, 0.005, 0.05, 0.1	1/m
	SWCC parameter g_n	1.3	-	-
	Saturation degree at residual saturation S_r	0.2	-	-
	Saturation degree at full saturation S_s	1.0	-	-
	Saturated permeability k_s	10^{-4}	10^{-5} , $5 \cdot 10^{-5}$, $5 \cdot 10^{-4}$, 10^{-3}	cm/s
Geotechnical	Effective friction angle $\phi'^{(*)}$	$\mu = 22$	COV = 10% ($\sigma = 2.2$)	°
	Effective cohesion $c'^{(*)}$	$\mu = 40$	COV = 20% ($\sigma = 8$)	kPa
	Unit weight γ	17	-	kN/m ³
Rainfall	Rainfall intensity q	3.6	1.8, 2.4, 4.8, 6.0	mm/h
	Rainfall duration t	48	-	h
(*) Treated as random variables following normal distributions				

4. Slope stability analysis

4.1. Baseline model

The baseline analysis employed the geometry of Figure 2 and the reference parameters of Table 1. Figure 3 illustrates the critical slip surface and the corresponding Safety Factor (SF) before ($t=0$) and after two days of rainfall ($t=48h$). The initial slip surface is typical, relatively deep, covering the whole slope from the toe to the crest and mobilizing a large soil mass. After the rainfall, a much smaller slip surface becomes critical. This surface is more local, located near the toe, and has a smaller sliding length and mass than the initial one. Notice that smaller and shallower failure mechanisms are common after rainfall events (Babu and Murthy 2005; Cho and Lee 2002). Nevertheless, due to the considerable depth of the excavation (150m),

the critical slip surface after the rainfall is still significant. It has a height of 56m and a depth of approximately 30m.

The rainfall caused a decrease in the SF and an increase in the P_F . Changes in the SF and P_F are attributed to the decrease of negative pore-water pressures (suction stresses) and the development of positive ones into the slope due to rainwater infiltration. As the water table rose at the slope's face from the toe and up, suction stresses became zero, and pore pressures increased, causing the relatively local slip surface of Figure 3(b) to become critical.

The effect of rainfall on the slope safety conditions associated with the initial critical slip surface ($t=0$) is negligible since the related factor of safety and probability of failure values remain practically unchanged after rainfall ($t=48$). In particular, the deterministic safety factor SF reduces from 1.22 (before rainfall) to 1.21 (after rainfall), whereas the probability of failure barely increases from 2.90% to 3.72%. This remark further underlines the significance of the downscale transition of the critical slope's failure mechanism after rainfall in deep excavations.

This change in the critical slip surface's location is highlighted as the critical effect of rainfall under the present conditions. This effect could be briefly described as a transition from a typical to a local failure mechanism. Note again that the local surface is 56m high and is critical for practical purposes, posing a significant hazard. Furthermore, it is probable that if this local failure happens, the upper part of the slope will also be affected, eventually leading to a massive failure.

Figure 3. Location of the critical slip surface and distribution of pore pressures: (a) at the initial state and (b) after two days of rainfall

The effective friction angle and cohesion were varied to calculate the probability of failure (P_F) from the Monte Carlo Simulation method (see section 2); the critical slip surface was kept constant during this process. Initially, baseline analysis provided the appropriate number of MCS trials for accurately computing the probabilities of failure. Figure 4 presents the mean SF and the probability of failure with the number of trials; 20,000 realizations were used herein and are adequate for producing converging results.

Figure 4. MCS procedure convergence plot before ($t=0$) and after two days of rainfall: (a) mean safety factor, $\mu[SF]$, and (b) probability of failure, P_F

Figure 5 illustrates the baseline model's SFs distributions prior ($t=0$) and after the rainfall ($t=48\text{h}$). The mean SF of the MCS equals the deterministic SF, further validating the adequate number of trials. The critical slip surface's change after the rainfall is accompanied by a noticeable decrease of the SF (from 1.22 to 1.15) and a noteworthy increase of the P_F (from 2.9% to 10.9%), suggesting a slope stability deterioration. Both these alterations imply the reduction in slope stability due to the rainfall; however, they do not reflect this effect with the same profoundness. Notably, a slight change in the SF of approximately 6%, but relatively close to the stability limit, corresponds to one order of magnitude alteration in the P_F . Therefore, P_F can reflect more appropriately slope stability changes over SF, which solely quantifies the margin of safety conditions from the critical state.

Overall, the minimum and maximum SFs slightly shifted after the rainfall, denoting that the SF distribution does not change much but only shifts towards smaller values. The standard deviation of the SF distribution does not change after the rainfall, leading to different COVs

before and after due to the mean SF difference. Finally, the reliability index for the normal distribution of the SF decreases significantly after the rainfall, similarly to the P_F .

Figure 5. Statistical distributions of safety factors: initial (t=0) with black line, and final (t=48h) with grey line

4.2. Slope height

Slope height is a very influential parameter in slope stability. Figure 6(a) presents the effect of height on the safety factor (SF) before the onset of rainfall (t = 0) and after its end (t = 48h). Figure 6(b) similarly illustrates the effect of height on the probability of failure (P_F). The SF decreases, and the P_F increases with the slope height in both cases.

Typically, the primary mechanism due to rainfall that affects slope stability is related to the suction profiles and the permeability gradients in the unsaturated zone. Specifically, as the slope height increases, the extent of the unsaturated zone also increases, noticing that the initial water table left boundary limit (H_w) remains constant. Moreover, suction stress in the

unsaturated zone also increases, and the unsaturated soil saturation decreases, resulting in much lower unsaturated soil permeability, especially near the ground surface. Overall, as the slope height increases, less rainwater infiltrates the slope, so stability is less affected by the rainfall event.

Nonetheless, as the groundwater table approaches the slope's face near the toe, this effect becomes less intense. In the case of deep excavations, the SF's decrease after the rainfall is primarily due to the critical slip surface shift towards this area, as presented in the previous subsection. The suctions near the toe are low, and the unsaturated permeability is close to the saturated one. As a result, the rainfall leads to a relatively rapid mound of the groundwater and the generation of positive pore-water pressures, resulting in the local failure mechanism of Figure 3b.

The initial slip surface is practically very similar to the one in Figure 3(a) for a slope height up to 150m. For deeper excavations (slope height larger than 150m), the initial slip surface does not reach the ground surface but appears on the slope, lower than the crest. For the 175m height, the height of the initial slip surface is 135m, and for 200m, the slip surface height is 110m. This surface height is directly related to the initial groundwater conditions. The relation between the slope height and the final slip surface remains approximately equal to 37%, i.e., for 100m, the final slip surface has a height of 37m, for 150m, 56m, for 200m, 74m. As a result, the relation between the initial and the final slip surface changes for slope heights more than 150m.

The effect of this mechanism (typical to local slip surface) on the SF is practically a decrease of 0.08 regardless of the height, overall denoting a 6%-7% decrease. This decrease appears small, but because the SFs before rainfall are relatively close to critical, even this change is significant. For example, for $H=200$, $SF=1.14$ before rainfall, and $SF=1.07$ after; this is a minor change in absolute SF values but might lead the slope to fail, thus being extremely critical. In

that vein, although as the height increases, the decrease in absolute SF values due to rainfall is negligible, the actual SF decrease becomes more critical as the initial SF was closer to the critical one for larger heights.

The probability of failure can reflect this even more clearly (Figure 6(b)). Although the slope becomes less affected by rainfall as the height increases, slope safety decreases dramatically for larger heights. For 200m height, the P_F increases from 10% to 30% after the rainfall (3 times), while for 100m, it increases from 0.2% to 5% (25 times). However, the change in P_F from 10% to 30% is crucial, while the change of 0.2% to 5% is not so much. For instance, guidelines for open-pit reliability analysis suggest a probability limit of less than 1.5% for long-term slopes, a limit of $P_F=1.5\%-5\%$ for medium-term slopes, and a limit of $P_F=5\%-10\%$ for short-term slopes (Kirsten 1983; Read and Stacey 2009). Thus, for 100m, the slope remains inside the limit for short medium-term slopes, while for 200m, the change is so significant that it renders the slope unsafe in any case.

In other words, even though the deterioration of slope safety due to rainfall is less intense for higher slopes, the latter shows a higher risk of failure, and thus, the rainfall's effect is more vital for them. Overall, both the SF and P_F describe the same effects. However, since the conventional safety factor is more difficult to interpret, the probability of failure is a more appropriate indicator. Both SF and P_F will be presented in the following, but the P_F will be predominantly analyzed.

Figure 6. Influence of slope height, H , on (a) the deterministic safety factor, SF , and (b) the probability of failure, P_F , during rainfall

4.3. Slope inclination

In surface mining, an important design parameter is the total slope angle. Its selection is commonly based on optimization studies (Zevgolis et al. 2018); even a slight steepening of the overall slope angle for two degrees may double the probability of failure (P_F). Practically for all angles, the initial and final slip surfaces (before and after the rainfall) are similar to those of Figure 3. Only for the steepest angle of 16° there is a smaller initial slip surface that corresponds to 90% of the slope height, however, without affecting the overall trends.

Figure 7 presents the P_F within a small - but crucial - range of slope angles for deep excavations. As the angle increases, P_F increases significantly before and after the rainfall. In particular, before rainfall starts, the P_F rises from 0.2% to 12.6%, for a slope angle increase 12° - 16° ; after rainfall ends, the P_F increases from 0.9% to 31.2%. The considerable increase of the P_F for a 4° change in the slope angle highlights the significance of this parameter.

Similar to the slope height, as the slope angle increases, the effect of the rainfall on the stability increases. For 12° , the P_F increases from 0.2% to 1% after the rainfall (5 times), while for 16° from 12% to 30% (2.5 times). Increasing the P_F from 12% to 30% jeopardizes the slope's safety, while changes from 0.3% to 2% are not crucial. Again, like for height, although steeper slopes are less susceptible to the effect of rain, they are less stable, showing higher initial probabilities of failure. As a result, although the influence of rainfall on the deterioration of slope stability is more pronounced in flatter slopes, the steeper slopes are principally associated with higher risks of failure.

Figure 7. Influence of slope angle, a , on the probability of failure, P_F , during rainfall

4.4. Rainfall intensity

Typically, as the rainfall intensity increases, slopes become more unstable. Figure 8 displays the probability of failure with time for various rainfall intensities q . The intensity was varied to evaluate its influence on the P_F , mainly to obtain the order of magnitude change, i.e., how much P_F can increase on a deep excavation by increasing the rainfall intensity. Before rainfall

starts ($t = 0$), the P_F denotes the initial probability of failure. A constant rainfall intensity q was used for all analyses to keep the generality of the results. This rainfall intensity was varied from very low (1.2 mm/h) to the upper limits of moderate (6 mm/h) (Office 2007).

Notice that the total rainwater height largely governs the conditions after rainfall, particularly the water that infiltrated the slope. Total rainwater heights varied from 57.6 mm to 288 mm for two days of 1.2 mm/h and 6 mm/h rainfall intensity. The total amounts of rainwater infiltrating the slope after 48h of rainfall are 26.1 mm (45%) and 126.6 mm (44%) for rainfall intensities equal to 1.2 mm/h and 6 mm/h.

The very low intensity (1.2 mm/h) did not affect the stability, and thus, the probability of failure was practically constant for that case. Nevertheless, the final slip surface changed to a smaller one, reaching approximately 75% of the slope height. There was no significant change with respect to the baseline results of Figure 3 to the slip surface for all other rainfall intensities. For the highest rainfall intensity (6.0 mm/h), at the end of the rainfall ($t = 48\text{h}$), the P_F increases significantly from 3.1% to 31%. This highest intensity corresponds to $q/k_s=1.67$, and a large amount of rainfall already becomes runoff water. Larger rainfall intensities would amplify further its effect; however, given the high q/k_s value, a significant decrease of SF or increase of P_F is not expected. It is demonstrated that for the examined range of rainfall intensities, covering the classes of events of low-to-moderate intensities, the alterations in slope safety are significant. This outcome highlights rainfall intensity as a decisive parameter in the stability of excavated slopes.

Figure 8. Influence of rainfall intensity, q , on the probability of failure, P_F , during rainfall

4.5. Initial groundwater table

A steady-state flow defined the initial groundwater table depth ($t = 0$) (see section 2). The crucial parameter in that definition is the total hydraulic head H_w at the left boundary - behind the slope's crest - of the steady-state seepage model (measured from the ground surface). Figure 9 illustrates the decrease of the P_F with H_w before and after the rainfall; lower H_w corresponds to a higher groundwater table, lower SF, and hence, higher P_F .

As H_w increases (i.e., the groundwater table becomes lower), the rainfall causes the P_F to increase slightly less intensely. For $H_w=10$ m, the P_F rises from 6% to 24% (four times), denoting critical slope stability, while for $H_w=40$ m, from 0.4% to 0.9% (more than twice). This trend implies that the rainfall effect is more profound on the stability of slopes with high initial groundwater tables.

Figure 9. Influence of groundwater table depth, H_w , on the probability of failure, P_F , during rainfall

4.6. Soil permeability

For slopes with low permeability soils, instability during rainfall is mainly attributed to the dissipation of suction stresses rather than groundwater table mounding. This work investigates a slightly different critical failure mechanism triggered by rain infiltration (see section 4.1). Nevertheless, the rainwater infiltration process governs the slope's stability evolution, whereby the soil saturated permeability, k_s , plays a key role (Rahardjo et al. 2007). Figure 10 depicts the change of the probability of failure P_F with time t , for k_s values ranging between 10^{-5} to 10^{-3} cm/s. Before the rainfall, the P_F remains constant since slope stability is independent of the soil's permeability. After the rainfall, the P_F significantly increases from 2.9% to 22.9% for the highest $k_s=10^{-3}$ cm/s. As the soil's permeability increases, more rainwater infiltrates into the slope for a given time interval, dissipating existing suction stresses, raising the groundwater near the slope's face faster, and ultimately deteriorating the slope's safety. Moreover, for the low range of k_s values ($k_s \leq 10^{-4}$ cm/s), the difference on P_F

after one day (24h) of rainfall is negligible; just only after two days of rainfall the difference on P_F becomes notable. This also highlights the importance of rainfall's duration in slope safety, complementary to the soil's saturated permeability. Overall, the numerical results demonstrate the significance of the saturated permeability in the safety of deep excavations during rainfall, similarly to typical slopes of smaller heights (e.g., Rahimi et al. 2010).

Figure 10. Influence of saturated permeability, k_s , on the probability of failure, P_F , during rainfall

4.7. Soil-water characteristic curve

The influence of the soil-water characteristic curve (SWCC) in slope safety is, herein, examined only by the shape parameter g_a , which denotes the suction where the air starts intruding into the soil ($S_e < 1$). This parameter drastically affects the unsaturated soil's response and the rainfall infiltration process (see Eq. (1)), so it is essential for slope stability evolution during rainfall. Different g_a values correspond to much different effective saturation and unsaturated permeability distributions in the unsaturated zone. This effect can also be evaluated by the slip surface before rainfall. For low g_a (less than 0.01), the initial slip surface corresponds approximately to 75% of the total slope height due to the changes in the pore pressure in the

unsaturated zone; this becomes 100% for $g_a \geq 0.01$. On the other hand, for high g_a (more than 0.01), the final slip surface (after the rainfall) increases with the g_a , being 37% of the slope height for $g_a < 0.01$, 43% for $g_a = 0.05$, and 54% for $g_a = 0.1$.

Figure 11 shows the effect of g_a on P_F before ($t=0$) and after the rainfall event ($t = 48h$). The SWCC and the parameter g_a insignificantly affect the initial SFs, which are almost equal for the various g_a . The observed differences are because the various g_a correspond to slightly different distributions of initial suction stresses (and shear strengths) in the unsaturated zone and, thus, slightly different critical slip surfaces. As a result, the SFs are practically equal, leading to similar P_{Fs} , implying equivalent levels of risk, while variations in the initial P_{Fs} (ranging between 2.5 and 3%) are unimportant. The more significant variations in the initial P_F over the SF denote the strongly non-linear relationship between these two indicators. In general, slight alterations in SF might correspond to larger variations in P_F , which is why P_F is commonly regarded as a more insightful indicator of slope safety conditions. This non-linearity is particularly intense near the area of $SF < 1.3-1.2$, which is often the case of design SF (e.g., Zevgolts et al. 2018).

The trend of Figure 11, i.e., the decreasing P_F with the increasing g_a , denotes the more intense deterioration of slope safety for low g_a during rainfall. As g_a decreases, the effective saturation, S_e , increases for a given level of suction stress, u_w . Hence, the permeability within the unsaturated zone, k_w , increases, approaching the saturated value, k_s , as g_a obtains very low values. Therefore, as the g_a decreases, more rainwater infiltrates into the slope in the same period, and the slope's stability worsens faster with the rainfall.

Figure 11. Influence of the SWCC parameter g_a on the probability of failure during rainfall

5. Conclusions

The effect of precipitation on the slope stability of deep excavations (e.g., mining excavations often up to 200m deep) has been so far investigated mainly indirectly, e.g., based on empirical observations and correlations between rainfall and slope movements. Nonetheless, rainfall events are often the reason for slope instabilities and failures, while the primary mechanism is related to the rainfall infiltration in the soil and requires special attention. In the present work, the slope stability of deep excavations under rainfall infiltration was thoroughly examined through an extensive numerical investigation. This study employed typical examples of lignite (brown coal) mining deep excavations (up to 200m) on fine-grained soils. In this work, the critical mechanism was the development after the rainfall of a smaller and more local than the initial (before rainfall) slip surface, due to the groundwater rise on the slope's face, from the toe upwards. Although this is a smaller and more local slip surface than the initial one, it is still more than 50m high, which denotes a significant hazard. This local type of failure is in accordance with similar, shallow failure surfaces presented in the literature and

is generally anticipated as the slip surface for deep excavations after rainfall. Furthermore, if such as significant soil mass fails, the consequences on the total stability will be crucial, and general failure of the slope should probably be expected.

For the baseline model, based on average values, the critical slip surface's change after the rainfall led to a decrease of the SF and an increase of the P_F , as expected. Both imply the deterioration in slope stability conditions due to the rainfall; however, the probability of failure better reflected the effect of rainfall. Overall, the minimum and maximum SFs slightly shifted after the rainfall, denoting that the SF distribution does not change but only shifts towards smaller values. The standard deviation of the SF distribution does not change, leading to different COVs only due to the mean SF.

The relative importance of involved parameters that influence the initial and especially the final slope safety due to rainfall was studied through a parametric analysis. Initially, the two geometrical parameters (slope height and inclination) were evaluated. The slope height has a significant influence on the rainfall effect on stability. Although the slope is less affected by rainfall as the height increases, slope safety decreases dramatically for more considerable heights. Even though the absolute change in the SF or P_F due to rainfall is less intense for higher slopes, these slopes have a higher risk of failure, and thus, the rainfall crucially affects them. Similarly, as the slope angle increases, the effect of the rainfall on the stability decreases in absolute values but may jeopardize the stability of the excavations.

The rainfall's intensity varied from the lower to the upper limit of moderate rain (1.2mm/h to 6mm/h). As the intensity increased, the P_F also increased because the infiltration in the soil was more intense at the same period. The minimum P_F was about 3% and the maximum 30%, showing an order of magnitude change as the rainfall got more intense. Furthermore, the initial location of the groundwater level, defined by two limits at the model's boundary and

the slope's toe, had a substantial effect. The observed trend implied that the rainfall effect is more profound on the stability of slopes with high initial groundwater tables.

The soil's saturated permeability significance was manifested in deep excavations. The P_F after the rainfall showed a considerable increase with increasing saturated permeability. For a typical fine-grained permeable range of 10^{-5} cm/s to 10^{-3} cm/s, the P_F increased from 5% to 20%. Finally, the shape of the soil-water characteristic curve was represented by the air-entry parameter g_a . A noteworthy increase in the P_F after the rainfall was noticed with decreasing g_a values.

Overall, the stability of deep excavations was investigated, highlighting the importance of each of the involved parameters. The slope's geometry (height and inclination) is critical for stability and dominates the rainfall results, primarily through the initial slope conditions and secondarily through their effect on infiltration. The rainfall intensity q and the soil permeability k_s have a most critical impact on stability, crucially affecting the infiltration process. The initial groundwater table is also critical for the initial stability but affects the infiltration process in many ways. Finally, the unsaturated zone's properties, quantified herein mainly through the SWCC parameter g_a , have a noteworthy but not critical effect. This study can serve as a basis for similar preliminary analysis for deep excavations in practice. Stability and reliability analysis reveals the need to support conventional safety factors with the probability of failure for a broader overview.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper

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